

Sensory Modality in Hebbian Neural Networks for Slope Locomotion Learning

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Keywords: Hebbian learning, Gecko-inspired robot, Sensory loss, Sensory modality, Neural plasticity

Abstract

Biological systems exhibit remarkable resilience, adapting to injuries through neural plasticity, a critical ability of the nervous system to adjust its connections in response to various stimulations. A fundamental concept in this area is Hebbian plasticity, which suggests that synaptic strength is dependent on the activities of the connected neurons. Previous research has demonstrated that incorporating Hebbian learning rules can enable networks to adapt and solve new tasks without domain randomization [1], while conventional gradient-based methods such as Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) often rely on domain randomization during training to achieve robustness.

This paradigm has been successfully applied to complex, animal-inspired robots, creating plastic neural networks capable of zero-shot generalization to out-of-distribution conditions, such as morphological damage and uneven terrain [2]. Additionally, recent work has investigated the Hebbian control networks to produce adaptive locomotion in legged robots, demonstrating their effectiveness in generating robust gaits even when shuffling the output of control network [3]. Although these studies have powerfully demonstrated adaptability to challenging tasks, our work investigates a different, complementary dimension: the sensory modality. We aim to investigate how different sensor modalities, specifically the inertial measurement unit (IMU) and foot contact (FC) sensors, influence a Hebbian neural network's ability to learn robust locomotion on sloped terrains. This paper systematically investigates the roles of distinct sensory modalities, highlighting which are most informative for acquiring stable gaits.

Our experiments are conducted on a simulated 19 degree-of-freedom (DOF) gecko-inspired robot equipped with two types of sensors: an IMU that provides three values including roll, pitch, and yaw of robot's body, and four foot-contact sensors that indicate ground contact for each foot. We use a feedforward neural network with an input layer of 7 neurons and output 19 values for motors commands. The network is fully connected and has a single hidden layer of only 16 neurons (see Fig. 1a). All the network's weights are determined by the Hebbian learning rule where its parameters

Figure 1: (a) An overview of the sensor impairment experiment using a simulated gecko robot walking on flat terrain and climbing slope angle. (b) Observed behavior of a learned policy under each sensory-loss condition. The robot walking trajectory, (x,y) coordinate in world frame, over 1000 simulation timestep started from the blue cross and ended at the green star and reds indicates sensor cut which is also highlighted in the red box. (c) The comparison of final reward in learning a stable gait under three different initial sensor conditions: Full Sensors, FC only, and IMU only across three different slope degrees.

are optimized using Evolution Strategy (ES)[2]. The optimization is subjected to 3 objectives; (1) maximizing the velocity in positive x-direction; (2) minimizing the rotational difference between the robot’s orientation and the terrain’s orientation; (3) minimizing the number of robot body collisions with the ground.

We designed two experiments to investigate the role of different sensor modalities in Hebbian neural networks. First, we test full-sensor policies under in-task sensor loss to investigate the sensor correlation in locomotion task. Policies are trained with full sensors (IMU and FC) at three different slope angles: 0° (flat), 10° , and 20° . For each terrain angle, we train 5 policies and evaluate these trained policies on the same terrain they were trained on but temporarily zero-out the IMU and FC signals for 300 time steps to investigate the immediate behavioral response during sensory loss and recovery when the sensors are reconnected.

This experiment demonstrates distinct roles for the IMU and FC sensors. As shown in figure 1b, when the trained robot (i.e., a trained policy with full sensors) loses its IMU signal mid-task, it begins to drift sideways, unable to maintain a straight heading. Once reconnected, it gradually corrects its orientation. Conversely, when the FC signals are cut, the robot stops moving but rapidly resumes its gait and continues moving forward once the signals are restored. These indicate that, for a policy trained with full sensors, the IMU primarily contributes to body orientation adjustment, while the FC is essential for generating a walking gait.

In the second experiment, we investigate the utilization of information from IMU and FC in learning slope locomotion. We train policies with three scenarios of sensory feedback: (1) full sensors, (2) IMU only, and (3) FC only. The training is repeated 5 times across all slope angles, and we evaluate each policy’s learning ability to converge to a successful walking gait, providing insight into which sensory modality is more informative for slope locomotion learning.

In figure 1c, we observe the policy learning performance through the averaged final reward for all scenarios, the higher the reward the better performance on forward locomotion task. The results show that policies with access to FC signals (both full sensors and only FC) achieve high final rewards and consistently achieve 100% convergence to a stable walking gait at all angles of slope. In contrast, the

policies using only the IMU signal show a decreasing trend in final reward as the slope's steepness increased and it failed completely on the 20° slope. This strongly confirms that foot contact provides essential sensory information for slope locomotion learning, enabling a robot to handle challenging steep slopes.

In the future, we will extend to the following: i) Deploy to hardware: Transfer our policies to the physical robot to validate our findings in real-world systems. ii) Enhance plasticity: Investigate more sophisticated Hebbian mechanisms to achieve truly online adaptation. iii) Investigate the effect of imbalanced sensory influence, arising from the binary foot-contact (FC) signal used in this work (+1 during the stance phase and -1 during the swing phase). iv) Experiment different failure modes such as noise and partial loss. v) Benchmark: Compare our method with other architectures to evaluate trade-offs in performance and adaptive capabilities.

Acknowledgments

The research was supported by the Super AI engineer and Fundamental Fund, Thailand Science Research and Innovation (TSRI, Grant No. FRB690039/0457)

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